

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: A Report from the PSDI Roadshow in Cambridge and Southampton

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Table of Contents

1	<i>Executive Summary</i>	4
2	<i>Background, Context, and Aims</i>	5
	Background and Context	5
	Aims of the Report	5
3	<i>Cambridge Event</i>	6
	Event Logistics	6
	Agenda and Speakers	6
	Summaries of the Presentations	7
	Cian Dingle, CCDC, “Welcome and Housekeeping”	7
	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “PSDI Introduction”	8
	Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Context: Data Curation Guidelines”	9
	Jennifer Gibson, Dryad, “Dryad: A case study in open data publishing for all fields”	9
	Kiera McNeice, Cambridge University Press, “Why research data matters to publishers”	10
	Clair Castle, Research Data Management, University of Cambridge, “Helping researchers to be FAIR: an institutional repository perspective”	12
	Chuck Cook, Global Biodata Coalition, “Data curation in the life sciences”	14
	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data accessibility in the chemical sciences: an analysis of recent practice in organic chemistry journals”	17
	Lightning talk 1: Kim Clugston, Research Data Team, Cambridge University Library, “Overview of the Data Champion programme at Cambridge”	19
	Lightning talk 2: Giulio Isacco Lampronti, Department of Materials Science & Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, “Powder diffraction data in scientific publications: collecting data from the past and guidelines for the future”	19
	Lightning talk 3: Chris Hunter, GigaDB Director, GigaScience Press, “GigaDB data curation (biological data)”	20
	Lightning talk 4: Mary Ann Tuli, GigaDB, GigaScience Press, “Working with authors prior to publication to ensure life science data meets GigaScience Press' standards”	21
	Lightning talk 5: Nishadi De Silva, BioFAIR, “Introduction to BioFAIR”	21
	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data Management Plans in Physical Sciences”	22
	Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Streamlining Data Curation: Lessons from Crystallography”	23
	Highlights from Small-group Discussions	25
	Data curation vs. data management	25
	Roles & responsibilities in data curation	26
	AI and automation in data curation	26
	Sustainability in data curation	27
	How could PSDI support data curation?	27
	Feedback Survey	28
4	<i>Southampton Event</i>	28
	Event Logistics	28
	Agenda and Speakers	28
	Summaries of the Presentations	29

Nicola Knight, University of Southampton, "Introduction to PSDI and Housekeeping"	29
Agnes Jasinska, DCC, "Context: Data Curation Guidelines"	30
Samantha Pearman-Kanza, University of Southampton, "Putting the R into FAIR Data - The complexities of FAIR data and the importance of Data Stewardship in the Physical Sciences"	30
Cerys Willoughby & Louise Saul, University of Southampton, "Data Management Plans for the physical sciences"	32
Aileen Day, University of Southampton, "Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards: Why and how?"	33
Lightning talk: Chris Taylor, University of Southampton, "Generation and curation of large quantities of predicted crystal structure data"	34
Simon Coles, University of Southampton, "Data management and FAIR standards: A crystallographer's perspective"	34
Matthew Partridge, University of Southampton, "Balancing Trust and Verification: Data auditing as the backbone of reliable chemistry data"	37
Richenda Houseago-Stokes, "Oceanographic Data Management"	38
Louise Saul, University of Southampton, "Data stewardship and the role of technicians/research technical professionals"	39
Highlights from Small-group Discussions	40
Data curation vs. data management	40
Challenges & pain points (and some possible solutions)	41
Roles & responsibilities in data curation	42
AI and automation in data curation	42
How could PSDI support data curation?	43
Feedback Survey	43
5 Conclusions and Next Steps	43
6 Appendices.....	44
Appendix A: Cambridge Event Web Page	44
Appendix B: Discussion Questions (Cambridge & Southampton).....	46
Appendix C: Cambridge Survey	46
The PSDI Cambridge Event Participant Survey	47
Summary of Results from the PSDI Cambridge Event Survey.....	48
Appendix D: Southampton Survey	49
The PSDI Southampton Event Participant Survey	49
Summary of Results from the PSDI Southampton Event Survey.....	49

1 Executive Summary

Robust data management and data curation practices are critical for reproducible research, and the growing volume of research data combined with the increasing complexity of tasks, tools, and skills involved only further underscores their importance. The task ahead is to examine and reflect on the existing domain-agnostic guidelines and best practices and tailor them to the needs of specific disciplines, including physical sciences.

Co-authored by the Physical Science Data Infrastructure (PSDI), the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), and the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC), this report presents the content and insights from two in-person PSDI Roadshow events on data curation and management in physical sciences: in Cambridge in June 2005 and in Southampton in July 2025. We offer the summaries of all presentations and links to presentation files, highlights from the discussions, feedback from the participant surveys, as well as recommendations for PSDI. The event agendas, promo materials, discussion questions, and feedback surveys are also included, to provide a blueprint for similar events in the future.

The two events brought together data curators, repository managers, data stewards, research support staff, research technicians, research data specialists, metadata experts, academic publishers, and data infrastructure specialists across physical sciences as well as from life sciences and environmental sciences in the UK. Each event included presentations on topics relevant to data curation and data management, including the development of standards in crystallographic data, application of FAIR data principles, metadata development, data auditing in the context of data collections, data management plans (DMPs), as well as the unique perspectives of research technicians, research support staff, repository managers, publishers, and data infrastructures. The discussions focused on defining data curation and data management, current challenges, roles and responsibilities, the role of AI, sustainability, and how PSDI can support data curation and management in physical sciences in the UK.

The following recommendations for PSDI emerged:

- Developing and offering a coherent set of domain-specific tools and resources, e.g., DMPs tailored to physical sciences.
- Gathering existing domain knowledge and technical skills and serving as an authoritative source of information on research data in physical sciences.
- Gathering case studies of such best practices to serve as exemplars.
- Developing their own training courses and materials on the relevant topics and to build the required knowledge and skills, or alternatively, identifying and promoting high-quality training produced by others.
- Working closely with community stakeholders to accurately represent their needs and interests, draw on their expertise, and stay current on new developments in the field.
- Serving as a community hub for physical sciences research in the UK by organizing events to facilitate knowledge exchange, networking, and community building.
- Establishing direct communication channels and collaborations with physical-science academic departments and professional bodies across the UK to raise awareness of PSDI's work and encourage engagement.
- Working closely with data repositories, academic publishers, and funders.
- Serving as a bridge between academia and industry in the UK.
- Setting realistic goals and timelines, assessing their progress and impact along the way, and sharing that evidence with stakeholders to build trust and authority.

2 Background, Context, and Aims

Background and Context

Robust data management and data curation practices are critical for reproducible research in physical sciences and other disciplines, and the growing volume of research data combined with the increasing complexity of tasks, tools, and skills involved only further underscores their importance.

A number of resources exist to guide such good practices – including the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles¹ for research data and other research outputs, and the Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology (TRUST) principles² for digital repositories. However, the guidelines these resources provide are often too general and domain agnostic, and therefore of limited usefulness to specialised, domain-specific research. Therefore, the challenge ahead is to gather, examine, and reflect on the existing guidelines and best practices around data management and data curation, and to determine how they can be adapted and tailored to the needs of specific disciplines.

The Physical Science Data Infrastructure (PSDI)³ project has taken up this challenge on behalf of physical sciences in the UK. Aimed at creating both the community of researchers dedicated to FAIR and reproducible research, and the first integrated data infrastructure for physical sciences, PSDI has been developing and making available a range of tools, services, data, and guidance to unify, support, and advance the discipline.

An investigation of the existing data curation guidelines and best practices of relevance to physical sciences is one of the current work streams within PSDI, and it is a close collaboration between PSDI, the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC)⁴, and the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)⁵. The PSDI Roadshow on Data Curation and Data Management in Physical Sciences described in this report is part of this work. It serves to engage physical-science community stakeholders from a variety of roles (researchers, data stewards, data librarians, technicians, publishers, and repository managers) and gather their inputs, experiences, and ideas on this important topic.

Aims of the Report

The primary aim of the report is to openly share the content of and insights from the two in-person PSDI Roadshow events on data curation and management in physical sciences – the Cambridge event in June 2005 and the Southampton event in July 2025. Toward that aim, the report contains the summaries of all presentations and discussions, links to presentation

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* **7**, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

³ Physical Science Data Infrastructure (PSDI) project: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/about-psdi/>

⁴ Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC): <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>

⁵ Digital Curation Centre (DCC): <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>

files, feedback from the participant surveys, as well as conclusions & next steps for PSDI and the wider physical sciences community.

Our secondary aim is to share a blueprint for a Roadshow event that could be reused and adapted to plan and deliver a similar event on data curation, data management, or a related topic of interest to physical sciences or other disciplines. To facilitate such reuse, we share the event web page and promo content, detailed event agendas, discussion questions, feedback surveys, as well as other event logistics, with the hope that the information will be useful to the community and will make the planning of stakeholder engagement events easier in the future.

Finally, we aim to introduce PSDI and the resources it is developing to the physical science research community in the UK, and to encourage researchers, data curators, data stewards, data librarians, technicians, publishers, funders, and other professionals in that research sphere to get involved in PSDI, in order to build community and foster knowledge exchange.

3 Cambridge Event

Event Logistics

The Cambridge event (*Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow @ Cambridge*) took place on 25th of June 2025 in the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC) in Cambridge. The event was jointly organized by the PSDI, CCDC, and DCC. The event was free to attend but required registration. Twenty people attended.

In addition to the event web page on the PSDI website⁶, the event was promoted via relevant email lists (PSDI, DCC, as well as several JISC lists), on social media (primarily LinkedIn), and via personal invitations. The information about the Cambridge event included in the web page and main promotion emails is provided in **Appendix A**.

Agenda and Speakers

The agenda for the Cambridge event, including the speakers and titles of their talks, is given in the table below.

Time	Session
09:30 – 10:00	<i>Registration & coffee</i>
10:00 – 10:10	Cian Dingle, CCDC, “Welcome and Housekeeping”
10:10 – 10:25	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “PSDI Introduction”
10:25 – 10:30	Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Context: Data Curation Guidelines”
10:30 – 10:45	Jennifer Gibson, Dryad, “Dryad: A case study in open data publishing for all fields”

⁶ Web page for the Cambridge event in the PSDI Roadshow: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/event/exploring-data-curation-and-management-in-physical-sciences-psdi-roadshow-cambridge/>

10:45 – 11:05	Kiera McNeice, Cambridge University Press, “Why research data matters to publishers”
11:05 – 11:25	Clair Castle, Research Data Management, Cambridge University, “Helping researchers to be FAIR: an institutional repository perspective”
11:25 – 11:40	<i>Coffee break + networking</i>
11:40 – 12:00	Chuck Cook, Global Biodata Coalition, “Data curation in the life sciences”
12:00 – 12:15	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data accessibility in the chemical sciences: an analysis of recent practice in organic chemistry journals”
12:15 – 12:40	Lightning talks + brief discussion
12:40 – 13:25	<i>Networking lunch</i>
13:25 – 13:40	Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Streamlining Data Curation: Lessons from Crystallography”
13:40 – 14:25	Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data Management Plans in Physical Sciences”
14:25 – 15:10	Breakout discussion session 1
15:10 – 15:25	<i>Coffee break + networking</i>
15:25 – 16:10	Breakout discussion session 2
16:10 – 16:25	Closing remarks and next steps

Summaries of the Presentations

Cian Dingle, CCDC, “Welcome and Housekeeping”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Wh7FBCrY1P2nL_xqkbsPjc0uFhmqu_NC/view?usp=sharing

Cian Dingle from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC)⁷ kicked off the Cambridge event with a welcome to participants, an overview of the agenda and some housekeeping, and an introduction to CCDC. He noted that CCDC is a world leader in structural chemistry data, software, and knowledge, serving a range of disciplines from materials science to life sciences around the globe. CCDC also manages the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)⁸, a comprehensive, curated database of published organic and metal-organic crystal structures, holding over 1.3 million structures.

⁷ The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC): <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>

⁸ The Cambridge Structural Database (CSD): <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/solutions/about-the-csd/>

Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “PSDI Introduction”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1HNnePvNluV43bvt5ESBg8URm040IU1hM/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Cerys Willoughby from the University of Southampton followed up with an introduction to the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)⁹ – what it is and how to get involved. Funded by the UKRI, the PSDI serves primarily the physical sciences in the UK, but the project products will be available openly to everyone. The drivers for PSDI are the barriers and challenges for physical sciences around data, technology, and human resources – anything from file formats not being interoperable to lack of skills and training. PSDI has worked with a diverse set of partners who have acted as Pathfinders for the project, identifying requirements and developing solutions to meet the needs of their communities.

The overarching goal of PSDI is to build a data infrastructure that works with existing systems and tools, and integrated with other research data infrastructures, allowing interdisciplinary research. Toward that goal, PSDI provides access to a large number of data sources and develops services and tools to help users to work with that data. PSDI also develops guidance, training, and case studies and undertakes a wide variety of activities to encourage knowledge sharing and collaboration within the community.

A selection of PSDI services and resources was highlighted, including:

- PSDI Data Revival Service – a free version of the software that can be used to scan paper lab notebooks
- PSDI Data Conversion Service – to address the issue of interoperability in the physical sciences

⁹ The Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI): <https://www.psdi.ac.uk/>

- Reproducible scientific workflows – including the development of tools to capture the full data provenance to allow reproducibility
- Knowledge Base – to provide guidance for physical scientists and those supporting them
- Case studies – to supplement the guidance
- Training activities – including in-person and online, webinars on various topics relevant to the community, and self-paced learning resources

Cerys stressed that PSDI is all about the community and encouraged the participants to get in touch at psdi@soton.ac.uk, join the mailing list, and get involved.

Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Context: Data Curation Guidelines”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1zMYI-MOp_Az5MngsUUSIGNpg5yDEJUfx/view?usp=sharing

Dr Ian Bruno, Director of Data Initiatives at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC), provided the context for the PSDI Roadshow. The goal is to get a better understanding of how PSDI can support data curation in the physical sciences in the UK. The goal is to explore the challenges, requirements, and best practices specific to data curation in physical sciences by bringing together data curators, research support staff, and researchers from the discipline and creating a forum to share knowledge.

The current outline of the report on data curation guidelines in physical sciences examines:

- What is data curation? How is it different from – or how does it overlap with – data management?
- Roles and responsibilities (and the skills & training required)
- Community benchmarks such as the CoreTrustSeal¹⁰ for data repositories
- Available guidance and best practices – general and domain-specific
- Case studies
- Interoperability and integration
- Community needs
- Recommendations for PSDI

Following his talk, Ian also introduced each speaker and moderated the Q&A and brief discussion after each presentation.

Jennifer Gibson, Dryad, “Dryad: A case study in open data publishing for all fields”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UEOJaei4Kmlqblp8MGue1cfDSB-GtwnN/view?usp=sharing>

Jennifer Gibson, the executive director of Dryad, offered a “peak behind the curtain” of her organization. Dryad¹¹ is an open data publishing platform and community committed to the open availability and reuse of research data. With good humour, Jennifer stressed that Dryad

¹⁰ CoreTrustSeal: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹¹ Dryad: <https://datadryad.org/>

is a platform, not a repository; a repository suggests repose and lack of activity, and the whole point is to make the data active again and keep it active via reuse.

Conceived in 2007 as home for a wide-ranging scope of data and backed up academic journals in 2011 with the Joint Data Archiving Policy (i.e., journals indicating to researchers that making research data available was a condition of publication), Dryad has been working to change the culture toward open data. Data does not have to be connected to a published paper anymore. In addition, while focusing on research data, Dryad will also publish research software if the researcher makes a convincing case for it.

Jennifer outlined three main strategies that Dryad uses to foster and support open data, including partnering with journals and publishers, providing a robust, cost-effective data-sharing solution for academic and research institutions, and ensuring that all research data is appropriately curated. She stressed the key importance of careful data curation by trained data curators to Dryad's mission and services.

Jennifer also gave a brief overview of Dryad's finances. As a non-profit, Dryad costs \$1.5 million USD per year to run, including 11 full-time (FT) and 3 part-time (PT) and freelance staff. In Jennifer's words, before the fees were revamped, "it was chaos." Working with a stakeholder-based advisor group to clean up the fees made a big difference. Now she and her team run Dryad as a non-profit service provider operating for the good of the community, and the current fee structure for using Dryad includes combined annual service fee and data publication fee, and discounted rates for partners.

Jennifer also offered some "food for thought" for the event's discussion sessions:

- Dryad was created by researchers, which created a big buy-in from the community
- Engagement with the academic publishing process is powerful
- Broad solutions have broad appeal – generalist vs. specialist
- Finances are best approaches with estimates of costs
- It is worthwhile to collaborate with existing services – and best to avoid compounding the challenges of sustainability for infrastructure

In response to a question about the data curators at Dryad, Jennifer emphasized that "the curators are the heart of what we do." She also argued that the data curators need to be full-time staff. Part-time staff tend to leave and take their knowledge with them, so it is not a good long-term approach. At Dryad, the data curators are thoroughly trained, with lots of checkpoints. They are also generalists by necessity, because all the data curation at Dryad is generalist, and every dataset is different.

Kiera McNeice, Cambridge University Press, "Why research data matters to publishers"

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1dQNro4dC_sqlyEQfRtXKZX-xWTdAuWIK/view?usp=sharing

Dr Kiera McNeice is the Research Transparency Manager at Cambridge University Press¹² and her role is advocating for and implementing best practices to support transparent, open, and reproducible research. Cambridge's mission is "to contribute to society through the

¹² Cambridge University Press: <https://www.cambridge.org/gb/universitypress>

pursuit of education learning, and research at the highest international levels of excellence.” Dissemination of research outputs that are robust and reliable is essential to that mission. Cambridge University Press is a non-profit publisher with a portfolio of over 400 academic journals in a board range of subject areas, from dance research to fluid mechanics.

Kiera started off by defining what each community wants. Research institutions want to maximise the impact of their researchers’ work. Research funders increasingly expect all research outputs to be publicly available. And researchers want to share (and get credit for) their work.

What does that mean for research data? Kiera argued that data associated with research publications should be available and intelligible to:

- Reviewers – to assess the reliability of the reported research
- Other researchers – to build upon the results of and/or collaborate with the authors
- The general public – to understand how the research results were obtained

What is the publisher’s role in all this? Speaking from the perspective of an academic publisher, Kiera listed the following tasks:

- To ensure that published research is robust and reliable
- To connect reviewers with research outputs – increasingly including data
- To advise society partners on policies and practices regarding research data
- To advise authors (researchers) on where and how to share their data

Kiera gave the example of the journal *Political Analysis*. In 2014, major political science journals decided that data related to each published paper should be available and issued a joint statement to that effect: *The Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT) statement*.¹³ Going beyond that, the journal *Political Analysis* requires all quantitative analysis to be reproduced before publication. To accomplish this, the authors must share data and code in a dedicated Dataverse instance, and a dedicated Replication Editor attempts to reproduce quantitative results. The authors may also use Code Ocean¹⁴ to ensure that their code runs for others.

From the publisher’s perspective, there are three main challenges:

- Where should researchers share their data?
 - Domain-specific repositories are not always available or known to authors
 - Generalist repositories may not suit specific requirements
 - Should publishers be “picking winners” by recommending specific repositories? What advice should publishers give?
- It’s too late to think about data when you publish
 - Retrospectively cleaning, curating, and annotating data can be a massive task
 - Data management needs to be baked into research projects from the start
 - Publishers only see one end of the research process
- Who reviews the data?
 - Peer reviewers are unpaid, often uncredited, often time poor

¹³ Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT): A Joint Statement by Political Science Journal Editors: <https://www.dartstatement.org/2014-journal-editors-statement-jets>

¹⁴ Code Ocean: <https://codeocean.com/>

- Not all journals/ societies can hire a dedicated Replication Editor (or pay for a third-party solution, e.g., CASCaD, the Odum Institute)
- Well-managed data, with good metadata, reduces the burden on reviewers

Kiera concluded her talk with three recommendations:

- Training for all researchers on good management of research data
- Clarity for researchers about where and how to share their data
- Good curation and description of published data (and this applies to any repositories and services that contribute to these tasks)

The discussion after Kiera’s talk focused on the importance of training in good data management as the foundation for good data curation. The participants also remarked on the benefits of data management plans and careful documentation of workflows and pointed out the need for a better connection and communication between researchers, facilities and technicians. Technicians are often responsible for data collection and have in-depth expertise in that area, but they are not consulted or included in decision-making as much as they could – and this disconnect can hurt both the research project and the data curation later on.

Clair Castle, Research Data Management, University of Cambridge, “Helping researchers to be FAIR: an institutional repository perspective”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-lhB0EmXxJZjHUFLm68i8jJlJF8hl6T/view?usp=sharing>

Clair Castle is the Research Data Manager at the University of Cambridge, supporting researchers across the University in recording, managing and curating research data, as well as in meeting funder requirements with respect to data management and data sharing practices.

In her talk, Clair focused on the institutional repository Apollo in the context of research data management (RDM) services at Cambridge. RDM services include supporting datasets deposits in Apollo, as well as a providing help desk, training, consultancy, and data management plan (DMP) review service. They also oversee the Data Champion programme.

As an institutional repository, Apollo is managed by the Open Research Systems team. Apollo runs on DSpace, an open digital repository system, is CoreTrustSeal certified, assigns DOIs for research outputs through DataCite, and follows the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles. Usage and citation statistics are tracked and displayed.

Clair shared some of these usage statistics in her talk, starting with the dataset deposits in Apollo per discipline over the last 5 years. As shown on the bar graph below (from slide 5), the School of Physical Sciences has more dataset deposits than any other school at the University (Arts and Humanities, Social Sciences, Clinical Medicine, Biological Sciences, or Technology).

Dataset deposits in Apollo - all disciplines, last 5 years

Moreover, within the physical sciences, Physics, Chemistry, and Materials Science have the most dataset deposits into Apollo (compared to Geography, Earth Science, Polar Research, Mathematics, or Astronomy; in fact, Astronomy had no dataset deposits at all). Is it because physical scientists generate the most data? Because they share and reuse data more? Perhaps, but one other possible explanation is that some disciplines (like Biological Sciences or Astronomy) may deposit their data into specialist repositories rather than in Apollo.

In terms of types of data that physical sciences are depositing in Apollo, lots of the data is derived from experimental instruments, there is a wide variety of proprietary formats, and lots of code is deposited alongside the data.

Clair also listed several challenges to FAIR data in physical sciences that she and her team have observed in their work supporting researchers. One challenge is that the research support staff often see the very end of the project, and the researchers' energy is gone at that point; they just want to publish the results and be done with that project. Metadata and documentation are often neglected. Proprietary file formats are also a challenge. Some researchers also overuse Supplementary Information to share their research outputs – but

Supplementary Information is not easily findable or properly preserved (no DOIs, published as PDFs, etc.).

In closing, Clair shared several ideas and recommendations on how to foster FAIR data practices and support good data curation:

- Training is essential (e.g., Research Skills Programme at Cambridge)
- Communities of Practice can be very powerful – including communities around Data Champions, Data Stewards, Data Analytics, Technicians
 - The Careers and Skills for Data-Driven Research (CaSDaR)¹⁵ project – led by Dr Samantha Pearson-Kanza and aiming to build a data steward network in the UK – got a mention
- Funders have an important role to play in promoting best practices in RDM, DMPs, and institutional policies
- RDM services are central to this work at each institution
- Conferences, events, and workshops are valuable – combining training with knowledge sharing and community building
- Published, peer-reviewed case studies that show the value of FAIR data (Researchers respond well to other research; they will pay more attention if something is in a peer-reviewed journal and evidence-based!)

Following Clair's talk, the group engaged in a brief discussion of the differences in licensing research data vs. research software, and the best ways to share, preserve, and curate research software. While depositing the code in GitHub facilitates reuse and continued development of the software, the fact that the content in GitHub is editable is a concern from the preservation and curation point of view. One option might be to deposit the code in GitHub, but also take snapshots of the code (a static record that cannot be edited) and upload that to a repository with a DOI.¹⁶ The importance of technicians' expertise and perspective in both data management and data curation was also brought up again (and became a recurring theme throughout the event).

Chuck Cook, Global Biodata Coalition, "Data curation in the life sciences"

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1tsCAMS07RUL19kMTdcCN4aLMisHam62e/view?usp=sharing>

In his talk, Dr Chuck Cook, Program Manager at the Global Biodata Coalition (GBC)¹⁷, provided the perspective of life sciences on research data curation. GBC is a startup NGO funded by and working on behalf of biomedical and life sciences research funders to help coordinate and sustain funding for the global infrastructure of biodata resources. More specifically, GBC provides a forum for research funders to better coordinate and share approaches for the efficient management and growth of biodata resources worldwide.

¹⁵ The Careers and Skills for Data-Driven Research (CaSDaR) project:

<https://zenodo.org/records/15835909>

¹⁶ Assigning a DOI to a GitHub release in Zenodo: <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/referencing-and-citing-content>

¹⁷ The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC): <https://globalbiodata.org/>

Chuck started off by outlining the long history of data sharing in the life sciences. He mentioned Atlas of Protein Sequence and Structure published in 1965. More recently, the funding for the FlyBase database (data on drosophila) was cut at the NIH, although the data will be preserved.

Life scientists have long shared their primary data by archiving it in specialist repositories. Added-value data curation (extracting information from the literature and adding it to the data) and analysis of primary data are at the heart of this work. We are talking about thousands of resources, coming from extensive collaborations and data exchange, and highly interconnected. Overall, life sciences data (or biodata) forms a rich and interdependent ecosystem that is supporting a large community of life science researchers all over the world. And the volume of research datasets is growing rapidly.

But there are many challenges as well. One challenge is the multitude of data types and standards being used in life sciences, from DNA/RNA/protein sequences, protein structures, expression arrays, molecular pathways, gene ontologies, genomes, proteomes, all the way to organisms and ecosystems.

GBC conducted an inventory of global biodata resources and found over 3700 biodata resources. Some very small, used by a single lab, but all with a website. Not surprisingly, given the costs of life sciences research the heaviest distribution of these biodata resources is in North America, Europe, and Japan. But the usage is more equally distributed, especially if you plot against the estimated number of researchers in that country. This is encouraging. Reuse is good. We want life sciences research to be cost effective; spending money to preserve and share the data is better than spending money to collect the same data over again.

Chuck also outlined several challenges for the biodata infrastructure, including the increasing demand, new technologies like AI, and not enough people in the system who have the data curation skill. He commented that the lack of data curation skills is partly a training problem but partly due to the loss of qualified people to other sectors that pay better salaries (e.g., banking, pharma). Sustainability challenges remain as well: funding is haphazard, short term, and unsystematically distributed; there is little global coordination among funders of these biodata resources; and infrastructure is not managed like infrastructure.

Added-value data curation is also interesting in itself. The term refers to a type of curation that goes beyond curating individual datasets or even collections. In added-value curation, curators extract information from the literature and put it in data resources, considerably increasing the value of these data resources to the community.

Chuck also outlined the exchange of curated data among ELIXIR Core Data Resources¹⁸ and between EMBL-EBI and external data resources¹⁹ (with graphs below to illustrate, from slide 12). Openness and connectivity amplify the value of resources manyfold.

¹⁸ Rachel Drysdale, Charles E Cook, et al. The ELIXIR Core Data Resources: fundamental infrastructure for the life sciences, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 36, Issue 8, April 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz959>.

¹⁹ Charles E Cook, Oana Stroe, et al. The European Bioinformatics Institute in 2020: building a global infrastructure of interconnected data resources for the life sciences, *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 48, Issue D1, 08 January 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz1033>.

copies be stored and who should take care of them? And what criteria should the data curation community use to make these decisions?

Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data accessibility in the chemical sciences: an analysis of recent practice in organic chemistry journals”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pKLGKM5bBmvpiV3sByDf8ZGfc4Gt9g2e/view?usp=sharing>

Dr. Cerys Willoughby returned to the presenter’s podium to talk about data accessibility in the chemical sciences, based on an analysis of recent practice in organic chemistry journals.

Cerys started off with an overview of the crucial benefits of sharing research data for scientific research. Sharing data facilitates progress in science because all research builds on the work done by others. Transparency allows verification and validation of results, which in turn allows reproducibility and reusability of research. Echoing previous talks, sharing data also means a more efficient use of resources – all the more important in times of tightening funding. Finally, open sharing of research data creates a fertile ground for both collaboration and innovation, while barriers to data sharing can hinder either outcome.

There are known issues with data sharing within the discipline of chemistry. First, it is difficult to find data that could be repurposed. It’s also difficult to validate and reproduce experiments, which leads to unnecessary duplication of experiments. There are limited examples of secondary analysis of open data. Lack of data also impedes the training of effective models for machine-learning. Low-yield results do not get published, which produces a bias in the published data. And the limited culture of data sharing gets in the way of collaboration.

Cerys listed several barriers to data sharing in chemistry, starting with unfamiliarity with data sharing concepts and not recognizing the benefits, through insufficient data management training, lack of time, and lack of incentives – to more practical barriers such as a high number of file formats from a variety of tools and instruments, lack of standards, concerns about sensitive data, and costs of data sharing.

To evaluate the state of play of data sharing practices in organic chemistry (specifically, access to data), Cerys and her colleagues studied 12 top journals in the field and 240 research articles in them, measuring shared data against the FAIR data principles.

The data sharing policies in the author guidelines of the journals revealed that: all the journals (12 out of 12) mandated sharing of crystallographic data in the Crystallographic Information File (CIF)²¹ format, 11 out of 12 recommended sharing all data in a repository, 9 recommended uploading the data to a subject-specific repository but offered little guidance, 5 provided additional advice for nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) data, and none suggested a repository for NMR data.

(It is worth noting the CIF is the standard format for storing crystallographic structural data. A CIF contains information about the crystal structure but also details of the diffraction

²¹ Short Guide to CIFs (CCDC): <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/community/access-deposit-structures/deposit-a-structure/guide-to-cifs/>

experiment and any data processing undertaken. The files can be read by both humans and machines. More about CIFs in Ian Bruno's talk.)

Cerys looked at each research article (240 papers total) and its associated data against the 17 FAIR variables. (See the screenshot below, taken from slide 7 in Cerys's presentation.)

FINDABILITY	ACCESSIBILITY
The dataset is deposited in an open repository	Coherent file structure (logically grouped and labelled files)
The associated article is cited or linked	README file describes the dataset
The dataset is assigned a unique, citable and persistent identifier (i.e., DOI)	Unprocessed primary data are included
All compounds are assigned a unique, citable and persistent identifier (i.e., SMILES or InChI + InChI key)	Metadata describe instrument parameters (vendor, model, version, software)
Data-time stamps for creation, deposition and versions of the dataset are included	Metadata describe experiment parameters
Bibliographic metadata are available (authors, contributors, affiliations, funding source)	Metadata describe data cleaning/analysis/processing/visualisation method(s)
INTEROPERABILITY	REUSABILITY
Original data are in standard open format(s)	Original data are in reusable format
Metadata are in a machine-readable format (i.e., XML, JSON)	Open licence information is available (i.e., CC or ODC) under which data can be reused
	Code scripts necessary to reproduce findings are available

Out of 240 articles examined, 239 produced data – but only 47 shared any primary data at all. Authors of only 4 papers uploaded data to a public repository of their own accord, and none used a subject-specific repository. Were all the compounds in the papers assigned a unique, persistent, and citable identifier (e.g., SMILES or InChI + InChI key)? No, not even one. This is despite the fact that the majority of laboratory software make use of them. Cerys also shared more detailed results of her analysis against each of the FAIR principles – and the results are not encouraging.

Only 8 papers shared primary data when such data sharing was not mandated. Adherence with the FAIR principles was only superficial, e.g., two articles provided README files, but they lacked useful metadata or documentation. Metadata was poor, incomplete, and mostly not in a machine-readable format. None of the articles contained structure identifiers for the compounds, only three papers had license information associated with the data, and only one paper shared any code.

Why is compliance so poor? Cerys argued that many factors are at play. First, mandatory requirements are effective in producing compliance – but if a journal only recommends a practice, that does not work. However, mandates are unpopular and some researchers will seek other journals for their papers in order to avoid mandates. Compliance is also poor because community standards are lacking, there are not enough trusted open repositories, and where guidance exists, it is not discipline specific and therefore of limited usefulness. On the other hand, the “publish or perish” culture mindset mean that researchers still mostly care about publishing papers, not data. Manuscript submission platforms still push researchers towards uploading their data in PDFs but could instead be pushing authors to upload their primary data to repositories.

To conclude, Cerys offered the following guidance for researchers in chemistry:

- Plan for data sharing up front – utilize data management plans (DMPs) to reduce effort in curation
- Share primary data in a public repository with a DOI
- Use open file formats
- Document data and share metadata
- Include a README
- Include license information
- Include structure identifiers

Lightning talk 1: Kim Clugston, Research Data Team, Cambridge University Library, “Overview of the Data Champion programme at Cambridge”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1CAWAk82nMKsQxJSdbpkz85Q14kv_aUEM/view?usp=sharing

Dr Kim Clugston is a Research Data Coordinator and member of the Research Data Team in the Office of Scholarly Communication at Cambridge University Library. In her lightning talk, Kim gave an overview of the Data Champions programme at Cambridge. Data Champions are volunteers from different roles across the University who share interest in research data management and help support the University's community of around 10,000 researchers. They act as local points of contact and help to advocate for and disseminate information about best practices in RDM, identify discipline-specific RDM needs, signpost to where to get help, and both undergo and offer RDM training. The web profiles of Data Champions²² allow researchers at Cambridge to find a Data Champion by expertise or discipline.

Lightning talk 2: Giulio Isacco Lampronti, Department of Materials Science & Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, "Powder diffraction data in scientific publications: collecting data from the past and guidelines for the future"

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/17D6dbCTbQNznw-R-ERA6pQMSoduCOfBd/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Giulio Isacco Lampronti is an X-ray Facility Scientist in the Department of Materials Science & Metallurgy at the University of Cambridge. In his lightning talk, he spoke about powder diffraction data in scientific publications from the perspective of facilities and technicians. The Materials Science & Metallurgy (MSM) X-Ray Facility²³ is a national research facility that serves the Cambridge research community as well as external academic and industrial users. MSM X-ray Facility provides a range of equipment, software, expertise, and training on the collection and analysis of structural data relevant to materials science. In this context, given large dataset sizes (e.g., high resolution images and videos), FAIR data principles raise pragmatic questions about financial and environmental sustainability.

²² Cambridge Data Champions search: <https://www.data.cam.ac.uk/data-champions-search>

²³ The Materials Science & Metallurgy (MSM) X-ray Facility at Cambridge: <https://xray.msm.cam.ac.uk/>

Giulio talked about past databases and data mining – and the lessons learned for the future. The goal is to make experimental powder diffraction data and associated information in the scientific publication more consistent and complete. How? Giulio suggested using powder diffraction data in FAIR format (CIF) and for CIF to also contain sample and data collection metadata. In addition, it may be important to consider associated materials properties, associated diffraction standard collections, and failed experiments and related information.

The discussion after Giulio’s talk returned to the importance of facilities and technicians in research in physical sciences, and including their perspective on and knowledge of data management and data curation in decision making during the project and in preparing publications at the end.

Lightning talk 3: Chris Hunter, GigaDB Director, GigaScience Press, “GigaDB data curation (biological data)”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/16kvkidVeh2VyyzwL8ghZ_FB8DI278MrX/view?usp=sharing

Dr Chris Hunter is the Director of GigaDB at the GigaScience Press²⁴, and he spoke about the data curation of biological data at GigaDB.²⁵ GigaScience Press is an academic publisher of journals in the life sciences domains. GigaDB is the data-curation and data-publishing platform of GigaScience Press. Both the journals and the database are fully open access. GigaDB contains over 2600 citable datasets that have been assigned DOIs and are available for public download and use.

Chris stressed that the key principle of all GigaScience Press journals is transparency, a major component of reproducibility. He used the matrix below to situate reproducibility relative to replicability, robustness, and generalisability in scientific research. Essentially, reproducibility is the ability to obtain the same results using the same methods and in the same data as the original research project (which supplied both the data and the methods). Moreover, reproducibility is the first step toward replicability, robustness, and generalisability – and transparency plays a key role here.

	Same Data	Different Data
Same Method	Reproducibility	Replicability
Different Method	Robustness	Generalisability

To ensure transparency and reproducibility of published articles, GigaDB:

- Provides a home for data that does not have a community repository
- Curates links to all data objects from their database
- Distinguishes between “data” (in a data repository) and “supplemental information” (a pdf or similar file associated with the article)
- Conducts data inspection to ensure that all data is openly available
- Follows FAIR data principles

²⁴ GigaScience Press: <https://www.gigasciencepress.org/>

²⁵ GigaDB, the data-publishing and data-curation branch of GigaScience Press: <https://gigadb.org/>

Chris also described the manuscript submission pipeline, pointing out the timing of data inspection (data made available to peer reviewers of the manuscript) and data accessibility check (data published publicly together with the accepted article).

Lightning talk 4: Mary Ann Tuli, GigaDB, GigaScience Press, “Working with authors prior to publication to ensure life science data meets GigaScience Press' standards”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fNsMOYHpl4el1v2i4224Mz1D_AyoMIPQ/view?usp=sharing

Mary Ann Tuli is the Senior Data Editor at GigaDB, working alongside Chris on data curation and data publishing of life sciences data at the GigaScience Press. Building on Chris's presentation, Mary Ann talked in more detail about the data inspection step in the manuscript submission process, and more broadly about how GigaDB data curators work with authors and editors, in order to ensure that the research data associated with every published article meets GigaScience Press's standards.

Lightning talk 5: Nishadi De Silva, BioFAIR, “Introduction to BioFAIR”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WrOTomNtEZUL6HRs4p7tiIWM8RQFb79Z/view?usp=sharing>

A computer scientist by training, Dr Nishadi De Silva is the Senior Technical Project Manager at BioFAIR,²⁶ In her lightning talk, Nishadi gave an introduction to BioFAIR and outlined the project's objectives. BioFAIR is a federated digital research infrastructure for life science researchers in the UK, funded by the UKRI. The goal of BioFAIR is to advance FAIR research data management, providing end-to-end FAIR research data management & analysis capabilities along with the necessary support and training for UK researchers working in the life sciences. As a digital research infrastructure, BioFAIR will integrate:

- Data repositories
- Compute engines
- Workflow orchestration
- Interoperability and APIs
- User support

In that way, BioFAIR will empower researchers in life sciences by allowing them to store data securely, access computing power, use shared tools, and collaborate more easily.

Nishadi also outlined BioFAIR's objectives:

- Culture change – to drive adoption of FAIR principles and open data across the UK life sciences to provide high quality FAIR datasets ready for uptake and reuse
- Access – to enable democratized access to data and data methods within UK life sciences via a national capability
- Defragmentation – to increase the coordination, collaboration, and cohesiveness of the UK's life science related data landscape, enhancing its effectiveness and efficiency

²⁶ BioFAIR: <https://biofair.uk/>

- Skills – to attract, develop, and retain excellent research data management skills and capacity for UK life sciences
- Data reuse – to improve the efficiency of research and enable new research by increased reuse of data in the life sciences

In closing, Nishadi also stressed that the UK BioCommons created via BioFAIR will involve data, methods, and people. Building a community of highly skilled practitioners is absolutely key here, and BioFAIR Fellowship Programme²⁷ is one initiative to support this work.

The discussion after Nishadi's talk focused on the similarities between BioFAIR and PSDI projects, and the importance of bringing the two project teams (or their representatives) together to exchange knowledge, compare challenges, solutions, and lessons learned so far, and look for synergies and opportunities to collaborate. Plans were made for a follow-up meeting including BioFAIR, PSDI, and DCC team members.

Cerys Willoughby, University of Southampton, “Data Management Plans in Physical Sciences”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IO-0Q-OwW6ArVTDYYMh6nTui7ao8kKbG/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Cerys Willoughby returned with an interactive session on data management plans in physical sciences. Cerys started off with an overview of the benefits of good data management plans (DMPs), but she acknowledged that there are many barriers as well. Too often, a DMP is something researchers do at the start of the project, because they are required to do it, but then they forget about it. DMP is not perceived as something useful to the project beyond the box-ticking. Adding to the problem, the available guidance tends to be general rather than domain-specific, and therefore not very useful.

PSDI aims to fill the gap and create discipline-specific DMPs for physical sciences. Getting access to good example DMPs from the physical sciences is a challenge, because there is a reluctance to share, the quality is poor, or the content is too specific to generalise for the whole community. Our approach was to make use of the discipline specific DMP template developed by NFDI4Chem.²⁸ The NFDI4Chem survey was developed following a DMP survey by an RDA working group, followed by another survey and a series of interviews.

Cerys and her colleague Dr Louise Saul drafted a DMP for the physical sciences community, based on the NFDI4Chem DMP, and added it to the Knowledge Base on the PSDI website (a temporary location)²⁹. But to take this work forward, feedback from the community is needed. One issue is that the current DMP is very long. What is useful? Which sections are the most important? What is still missing? What is unnecessary and could be cut? How could the DMP be improved in other ways (e.g., guidance, pre-generated text, integrations)?

At this point, Cerys shared a QR code to the online version and distributed printed copies of the draft DMP to the event participant, together with a list of feedback questions. The participants then spent several minutes reading the draft, commenting on it, and discussing it

²⁷ BioFAIR Fellowship Programme: <https://biofair.uk/biofair-fellowship-programme/>

²⁸ NFDI4Chem, the Chemistry Consortium within the NFDI: <https://www.nfdi4chem.de/>

²⁹ Draft DMP for physical sciences on PSDI website: <https://tinyurl.com/psdi-dmp>

in small groups, before a vevox poll was used to facilitate a whole-room discussion. Good engagement and feedback were provided by the group, including some consistent suggestions that can be used to help PSDI plan further work in this area.

In conclusion, Cerys encouraged the participants to get in touch with her with any additional feedback or suggestions they might have.

Ian Bruno, CCDC, “Streamlining Data Curation: Lessons from Crystallography”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RROZKZQhy4NUxm89oE9_eEDWiMaNWDuW/view?usp=sharing

The last presentation of the day (before the small-group discussion) was given by Dr Ian Bruno, Director of Data Initiatives at CCDC, and the topic was data curation in crystallography.

Ian started off by sketching the historical timeline of the topic, starting with early publication of crystallography data – first on paper, in articles, in the 1940s; then as a computer-based file of bibliographic information and numerical data first compiled in 1965, thanks to the funding from the Royal Society, and distributed as a series of printed volumes. The first databases consisted of manually transcribed tables of data from journal articles. Because manual data input is prone to errors, the first software developed around that time (1960s & 1970s) helped to check for such errors. This software was the beginning of early data curation tools.

Today, the data journey of a crystal structure consists of both automated and manual steps. In the first two steps, data is captured in a standard semantic and technical formats, then deposited in a crystallographic data repository.

Ian emphasised that there are several facets to a crystallography experiment: the sample, the equipment, the data, the software, the publication. Furthermore, each facet (or step) contains a lot of information that is crucial for the interpretation and reuse of the results and therefore needs to be captured and preserved accurately. For instance, the data can only be meaningful if linked to information about the sample from which it originates. (See the summary image below from slide 7 in Ian’s presentation.)

Crucial to the story of crystallography is the Crystallographic Information File (CIF)³⁰ – the community standard for information exchange and the *lingua franca* of the crystallographic research, developed and maintained by the International Union of Crystallography (IUCr).³¹ CIF serves as the semantic representation of crystallographic data and contains all the information needed to interpret and use this data:

- Details about the physical sample
- Equipment details
- Experimental conditions
- Software packages and parameters used
- Raw, processed, and derived data
- Publication details

The IUCr also hosts a CIF-based service that catches potential problems with crystallographic data: checkCIF.³² checkCIF generates validation alerts if it detects any of the following problems: required data is missing, inconsistencies in the data, the structural model is potentially incorrect, indicators related to the quality of the structure.

Another useful service is joint CSD/ICSD web deposition service³³, which enables researchers to deposit crystal structures (in the CIF format) ready for publication. The service guides the user through a multi-stage process to deposit their data, with checks, validation, and enrichment of the data along the way. For instance, duplicates can be detected – prior deposits of the same crystal structure already in the database.

Here Ian returned to the diagram showing the data journey of a crystal structure – now focusing on the last two steps: enrichment of data by expert data curators and ongoing enhancements to address changing needs of the field.

Ian talked about the importance of providing a 2D chemical interpretation of 3D experimental data, which is accomplished with a combination of automated and manual processing, and facilitates data discovery and reuse. When the chemical representation of a crystal structure is unclear, or there is conflicting evidence, the assignment of most probable bond types can be done automatically. Overall, a combination of automated processes and expert validation is still the most reliable, and human experts still play an essential role in discovering new knowledge and in enhancing the existing database entries.

Ian concluded his talk by listing several practices that enable good data curation in crystallography and that could also be effective when applied to other disciplines:

- Standard semantic file formats that are widely adopted by researchers in the field – as well as by key software tools and platforms
- Guidance, best practice, and services promoted by IUCr and adopted by publishers
- Data deposition workflows encouraging best practices by researchers and connecting to publication platforms
- Automated tools that enable the triage necessary to prioritise manual curation in the face of increasing throughput

³⁰ Crystallographic Information Framework and Crystallographic Information File (CIF): <https://www.iucr.org/resources/cif>

³¹ International Union of Crystallography (IUCr): <https://www.iucr.org/welcome.html>

³² checkCIF: <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989019016244>

³³ Joint CSD/ICSD web deposition service for CIF data: <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/deposit>

- Considering curation throughout the data lifecycle – from data generation through publication and beyond

Fittingly, Ian's last slide was an acknowledgement to "all who contribute to the development and adoption of standards, tools and services featured in this talk" as well as "the CCDC Data & Community team who make the curation happen."

Highlights from Small-group Discussions

The next part of the Cambridge event consisted of moderated small-group discussions. We used a pre-determined set of discussion questions (shared in **Appendix B**) to guide the discussion, but we allowed enough flexibility to follow the participants' unique interests and experiences for a more natural flow of conversation. Printed worksheets and a digital file for collaborative notes were provided. One or more PSDI, DCC, or CCDC team members served as a moderator and note taker at each table.

Data curation vs. data management

We kicked off the discussions by defining data curation and distinguishing it from data management.

There was a general consensus that data curation is a broad concept and encompasses multiple stages and tasks. It may also look different in different disciplines, depending on types of data and the data lifecycle. One key aspect of data curation is data preservation, but data curation also involves optimising the data for reuse and deciding what data to keep and what to discard. It may also involve validating the data (or "sense checking" it) or adding value to the data (e.g., by extracting information from the literature and linking it to a dataset). The role of a data curator is analogous to that of a curator in art.

The differences between data curation and data management were less clear and more debated. One way to distinguish data curation from data management is to consider the timing and aims of the activities and who carries them out. In that view, data management tasks happen during the research project and aim to ensure the success of that project. Data management is carried out by the project team. In contrast, data curation would typically happen after project completion, when the original research team uploads their data and associated project documentation to a data repository, for other researchers to find, access, and reuse it. In that view, data curation is carried out by data repositories (institutional, generalist, or domain-specific) rather than the original research team or institution responsible for collecting and analysing the data. The aim is to share the data with the wider research community and the public to encourage reuse and maximise the benefits to science and the society.

Data management and data curation might also involve different skills and tools. Some participants argued that data curation requires more knowledge and more information than data management. Curation requires expert oversight, although multiple types of expertise may be involved (subject expertise, archival expertise, etc.). Beyond preserving data and making it available for reuse, curators organise, document, make sense of data, and add value to the data.

The data curators in the group also pointed out the importance of customer service and interpersonal skills in data curation, in addition to the technical skills and domain knowledge focused on data itself. Curators work closely with at least two groups of stakeholders: the researchers who have collected the data and want to upload it to a repository (and may need help doing so), and the researchers, NGOs, policymakers, industry, and the general public who want to find, access, and reuse that data (and may need help doing so as well).

Roles & responsibilities in data curation

Who is responsible for data curation? The consensus was that the responsibility is shared—everyone is responsible, depending on their role and the point in the research data lifecycle when they are involved.

In some ways, good data curation starts with—and relies on—good data management. Therefore, anyone involved in managing the research data during a research project also contributes to data curation down the line. This includes all members of the research team (researchers, research managers, technicians, data stewards) as well as institutional research support staff at that institution.

Several participants also argued that research funders and academic publishers also share in the responsibility for good data curation, either directly or via good data management. For instance, both funders and publishers can mandate specific good practices (e.g., data management plans as part of grant applications, or uploading the data to an open repository as a condition of publication in a peer-reviewed journal).

On the other hand, any funder and publisher requirements will only be effective if the individuals responsible for data management and data curation have the necessary skills and knowledge to do their job well. This requires training. Carpentries are one model of community-driven training that proved very effective in other contexts. It also requires a two-way communication and knowledge exchange between the various roles (e.g., between researchers and data stewards).

AI and automation in data curation

At present, AI (particularly generative AI) is creating a lot of legal and ethical questions that data curators have to grapple with, and these questions are no longer abstract but very practical. But in the long term, these tools could be useful in automating some data curation tasks and assisting in others. For example, there is a role for machine learning (ML) in metadata generation. Similarly, data curators spend a lot of time checking file formats and instructing authors on the right file format to submit; this step could be automated.

Generative AI was at the forefront of everyone's mind. Participants mentioned the potential use of generative AI in reading and summarizing scientific literature or other information. They also reflected on generative AI scraping open data and other open knowledge resources and wondered whether it may constitute a valid and productive reuse of this information. While not necessarily built on generative AI, chatbots are also being tested as a more interactive alternative to FAQ but using the same information.

In addition, growing interest in ML projects for academic research means a new emphasis on solid data management and data curation practices. ML relies on good data and good documentation.

The consensus about AI was that these tools and technologies are here to stay, they are not going away, so the best approach is to learn to use them in the context of data management and data curation and to model how to use them well.

Sustainability in data curation

Another topic that, while not explicitly in the discussion questions, clearly emerged during the presentations in the morning and continued into the small-group discussions was sustainability. How to make data curation sustainable both in financial and environmental terms?

Regarding financial sustainability, participants agreed that a project-based funding structure is insufficient to support data curation long-term. What happens after the project ends? Who is responsible for maintaining and updating the resources? Where does the funding come from? These questions are important to ask for all data curation projects, but particularly for data infrastructure projects. How to maintain these infrastructures after they are built and made operational, but the project ends? There are various business models out there, but it is essential to plan for this stage from the start.

The questions around environmental sustainability are just as important. Storing, managing, and curating data is environmentally expensive. This means that it may not be sustainable – or feasible – to keep all the research data that is being produced. We will have to select which data to keep and which to discard. What criteria should we use to make these decisions? Who should make them and at what stage?

For example, in crystallography, raw data is often discarded. Only the 2D and 3D models are kept because they are most useful to the field. But sometimes the structures raise red flags and the issues cannot be resolved using only the models, we need to go back to the raw data. So the question is: How long should we keep the raw data? Do we keep it until the structure is verified, with no red flags – but we keep the raw data files until then? The large volume of the raw data means that there are limits to how long we can keep it.

Participants also discussed the difference between redundancy (good) vs. duplication of effort (bad). Sometimes we need to keep and manage multiple copies of the same dataset because of its importance and value to the scientific community. The goal is to protect the crucial data against loss due to technical, weather-related, or political adversity. Such redundancy is beneficial and helps to build resilience. But which datasets merit such redundancy? And at what point does it become a duplication of effort and a waste of resources?

How could PSDI support data curation?

Participants had many suggestions regarding how PSDI could support and advance best practices in data curation and data management in physical sciences, as well as about tools and resources that PSDI could develop.

Gap analysis of publicly available databases was one idea. Guides for researchers and research support staff on how to use repositories as well as guides aimed at people running the repositories could be useful as well. Interoperability and machine readability are two topics where guidance and training may be needed. More generally, PSDI could help develop standards and best practices in data curation and data management tailored to physical sciences and then offer training to disseminate and promote these standards and best

practices and to encourage their adoption. Training in a variety of formats might be beneficial, including Carpentry-style, hands-on courses.

Coordination, networking, and community building could be another essential contribution. PSDI could find people already involved in data curation and data management in physical sciences in the UK and bring them together; help to connect them and give them a forum to communicate and collaborate. For instance, PSDI could visit Chemistry departments and other professional bodies in the UK to increase awareness of its mission and work streams and build community. PSDI could also establish links, exchange knowledge, and collaborate with other domain-specific data infrastructures (e.g., BioFAIR). Finally, PSDI could serve as a bridge between industry and academia in the UK.

Feedback Survey

To gather participants' feedback and suggestions about the Cambridge event, we designed and administered a Google Form survey that included ranking questions (to obtain quantitative data) and open-ended questions (to obtain qualitative data). A copy of the Cambridge survey and a summary of results are provided in **Appendix C**.

4 Southampton Event

Event Logistics

The Southampton event (*Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow @ Southampton*) took place on 8th of July 2025 at the University of Southampton. The event was jointly organized by the PSDI, DCC, and the University of Southampton. The event was free to attend but required registration. Twenty-four people attended.

In addition to the event web page on the PSDI website³⁴, the event was promoted via relevant email lists (PSDI, DCC, as well as several JISC lists), on social media (primarily LinkedIn), and via personal invitations.

Agenda and Speakers

The agenda for the Southampton event, including the speakers and titles of their talks, is given in the table below.

Time	Session
09:30 - 10:00	Registration & coffee

³⁴ Web page for the Southampton event in the PSDI Roadshow: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/event/exploring-data-curation-and-management-in-physical-sciences-psdi-roadshow-southampton/>

10:00 – 10:15	Dr Nicola Knight, University of Southampton, “Introduction to PSDI and Housekeeping”
10:15 – 10:25	Dr Agnes Jasinska, DCC, “Context: Data Curation Guidelines”
10:25 – 10:45	Dr Samantha Pearman-Kanza, University of Southampton, “Putting the R into FAIR Data – The complexities of FAIR data and the importance of Data Stewardship in the Physical Sciences”
10:45 – 11:30	Drs Cerys Willoughby & Louise Saul, University of Southampton, “Data Management Plans for the physical sciences”
11:30 – 11:45	<i>Coffee break + networking</i>
11:45 – 12:05	Dr Aileen Day, University of Southampton, “Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards: Why and how?”
12:05 – 12:10	Dr Chris Taylor, University of Southampton, “Generation and curation of large quantities of predicted crystal structure data” (A lightning talk)
12:10 – 12:25	Dr Simon Coles, University of Southampton, “Data management and FAIR standards: A crystallographer’s perspective”
12:25 – 13:25	<i>Lunch</i>
13:25 – 13:45	Dr Matthew Partridge, University of Southampton, “Balancing Trust and Verification: Data auditing as the backbone of reliable chemistry data”
13:45 – 14:05	Dr Richenda Houseago-Stokes, Oceanographic Data Management
14:05 – 14:25	Dr Louise Saul, University of Southampton, “Data stewardship and the role of technicians/research technical professionals”
14:25 – 15:10	Breakout discussion session 1
15:10 – 15:25	<i>Coffee break + networking</i>
15:25 – 16:10	Breakout discussion session 2

Summaries of the Presentations

Nicola Knight, University of Southampton, “Introduction to PSDI and Housekeeping”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Z3skNMtPNYQVp-Lc5tuh0NAtNxGSP07H/view?usp=sharing>

The event started with an introduction to PSDI and some housekeeping information, delivered by Dr Nicola Knight, PSDI Coordinator and Senior Enterprise Fellow at the University of Southampton. (Please see the Introduction to PSDI talk in the Cambridge event section for details.)

Agnes Jasinska, DCC, “Context: Data Curation Guidelines”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iGex1Qlklmc_RZFsF4rf7SKlwR6gLY6/view?usp=sharing

Dr Agnes Jasinska, Research Data Specialist at the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) and the DCC lead on the PSDI project, gave a brief talk to explain the impetus and purpose of the Roadshow in the context of the PSDI work on data curation guidelines for physical sciences. (Please see the summary in the Cambridge event section for details.)

Samantha Pearman-Kanza, University of Southampton, “Putting the R into FAIR Data – The complexities of FAIR data and the importance of Data Stewardship in the Physical Sciences”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1K7Kb-3_vfA8Sv-ujssWN28ZQT9Eu8JoY/view?usp=sharing

Dr Samantha Pearman-Kanza is a Senior Enterprise Fellow at the University of Southampton, she is a Co-Investigator and a Pathfinder Lead for Process Recording for PSDI, as well as the Principal Investigator for the Careers & Skills for Data-driven Research (CaSDaR) Network+. She gave a talk on the reuse of research data and the importance of data stewards to physical sciences.

Sami started off by describing the current situation in physical sciences research: research data is growing exponentially but much of this data is stored in random places and cannot be located, or is unintelligible when found; this results in a lot of waste and preventing researchers from building on others' work. A key part of the solution to this is the FAIR data principles³⁵ that ensure that research data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. As part of this point, she shared a good motto: “Data, or it didn't happen.”

However, FAIR principles are very end-focused, i.e., focused on the end stage of a research project, namely, data sharing and reuse. Sami argued that this is a limitation and needs to be rethought. Instead of focusing on data sharing at the end of the project, we need to carefully consider how we create the data, so this data can be well curated, shared, and reused later on. The FAIR principles (including R for Reusable) are insufficient to guide us in that respect.

Firstly, it is not just about data – we need to consider and plan for the tools, code, methods, and context of our research projects as well. We need to consider whether someone can reuse our data in the same manner as we did; replicate our entire research project, including data collection and analysis; reproduce our results; or repurpose our data or software for a new endeavour. Both READMEs and metadata can be used to aid with this process, and it is important to understand the differences between them. READMEs can be used to explain how to make use of the data, and metadata can be used to define data attributes, terms of use, and provenance.

In other words, reuse of research data starts with the creation of that data. The FAIR principles will only be useful if the data is created in a way that makes it reusable in the first

³⁵ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

place. Many of the issues with data reuse start at the creation/ collection stage – and can also be prevented or mitigated at that stage. For instance, good data creation involves proper planning (DMPs). Moreover, well created/ collected data makes data curation easier as well.

However, this involves many tasks: acquiring DOIs, identifying relevant data repositories, setting relevant access levels and licensing for reuse, making data available in interoperable formats, and providing metadata and READMEs alongside the data. And these tasks in turn require a lot of knowledge and skills, including: data management planning, data collection, data curation, metadata generation and appropriate schemas for generic & domain specific metadata, ethics & governance, publication & data sharing, using repositories.

The question that Sami posed is: Should we really expect researchers to be experts in all of this? Is it realistic? The answer is: almost certainly not.

So, what is the solution? Sami argued that we need professionals with technical skills and domain knowledge to work with researchers to create FAIR datasets. In other words, we need data stewards. Data stewards play a role at every stage of research data lifecycle.

This image is based on Jisc's Research Data Lifecycle taken from - <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/guides/research-data-management-toolkit>

The challenge is that the profession of data stewards (in the UK and elsewhere) is not well established, even though staff members at many universities and research institutes fulfil these responsibilities without the job title. As a result, there is a shortage of skilled data stewards, and this needs to change.

This is where Sami's new Network+, the Careers & Skills for Data-driven Research (CaSDaR)³⁶ project, comes in. CaSDaR aims to build a community of data stewards in the UK, to establish data stewards as a profession and develop their career pathways, to promote the recognition of data stewards and their critical role in managing and preserving research data, and to enable sustainability of the project outputs by establishing Data Steward Association that will continue this work beyond the life of the project.

Sami also discussed the planned project deliverables, funding calls, and events, including the CaSDaR Launch Event on 18th September 2025 in Birmingham (immediately after the PSDI

³⁶ CaSDaR on LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/casdarknetwork/>

Showcase³⁷ on 17th September in the same venue; both events free to attend). CaSDaR also plans to connect and collaborate with other national and international data steward networks and supporting initiatives (with an international event for data stewards planned for 2026).

Sami concluded by inviting the participants to get involved by following the CaSDaR LinkedIn account or signing up for the mailing list (www.jiscmail.ac.uk/CASDAR). The project aims to make things better for data stewards and to progress data stewardship as a career!

Cerys Willoughby & Louise Saul, University of Southampton, “Data Management Plans for the physical sciences”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Df54wIRp8Cf_KsYP-o6L8-mn1gBSNsQW/view?usp=sharing

Drs Cerys Willoughby & Louise Saul conducted an interactive session on data management plans in physical sciences to gather feedback on the draft DMP they created as part of PSDI's work on data management planning. While introducing the topic, Louise commented that there are lots of good reasons to start thinking of research data very early on in the project - and data management plans are a great way to do it. (Please see the summary in the Cambridge event section for details.)

During the discussion that followed, the participants shared several ideas and suggestions with regard to the draft DMP for physical sciences:

- How to deal with missing data? Which section would that information fit into?
- More persistent identifiers: ORCIDs, research institutions, funders & grants
 - Are there IDs for methods and instruments? These could be included too
- Maybe information about the research project (aims, hypotheses, etc.) could be separate from funding & grant information
- Different sections and guidelines depending on the funder & grant (and matched to them)?
 - DMPonline has funder templates. Depending on the funder of the project that you select, the template asks for different information and provides different guidelines
- Costs section
 - When would researchers have this information, in order to fill it out? It seems that you need to know what you are planning, the team you will need, the equipment, software, storage, etc. before you can calculate the costs
- DMP is a whole-team document (or process; the document is the record of the planning) – so different people may be responsible for different sections (depending on their expertise and role in the project)
- Other suggestions
 - DMP template vs. DMP tool. A tool would be smarter and would assist more. Could the DMP tool take factual information about the project (project aims, methods used, types of data collected, project team needed) and actually assist with the planning based on that (including generating text, numbers, and

³⁷ PSDI Showcase on 17th September 2025: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/event/psdi-showcase/>

other information)? For instance, estimate storage needed, estimate budget for the project member salaries, etc.

Aileen Day, University of Southampton, “Plugging Physical Sciences research data into PSDI via metadata and standards: Why and how?”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/12crAOS4NoAOX-r9h6ZFhQ7kzs7vLgR8N/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Aileen Day is the Senior Data Engineer and Metadata Lead at PSDI, and her talk focused on adding metadata and standards to PSDI. Aileen referred to metadata as “the glue that holds PSDI together” – it keeps all the different parts and branches of PSDI together and links them via a common language. The metadata also reflects how things are organized inside PSDI. Resource themes, e.g., Pathfinders are one category to group the outputs. Within the resource theme, there are data outputs, services, tools, and guidance.

PSDI metadata is organized with a top-down approach. From the metadata about resources at the top of a pyramid, through the metadata about properties within these resources below it, then the metadata about data within the resources even lower, and finally the metadata about data provenance at the bottom. The metadata that support PSDI Resources Catalogue is separate from the metadata that supports PSDI Cross-Data Search.

Aileen emphasized that, wherever possible, PSDI metadata uses existing standards, ontologies, vocabularies, and community best practices, e.g., following the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)³⁸, designed to support the FAIR implementation of cross-disciplinary research in both human- and machine-readable fashion. PSDI metadata uses

³⁸ The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF): <https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html>

other existing standards as well, including SKOS vocabulary (for PSDI terminology), DCAT resource catalogue (for PSDI Resource Catalogue), and OPTIMADE (for PSDI Cross-Data Search). PSDI requires that the resource data aligns with OPTIMADE core properties and PSDI namespace properties for maximum searchability. Aileen demonstrated searching the PSDI to find a substance, and how OPTIMADE structure properties enable such a search behind the scenes.

Lightning talk: Chris Taylor, University of Southampton, “Generation and curation of large quantities of predicted crystal structure data”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_nawQ9z7X-u_qJjiNvOFcD2xMnUtlwuR/view?usp=sharing

Dr Chris Taylor from University of Southampton gave a lightning talk about the generation and curation of large quantities of predicted crystal structure data. One big question in crystal structure prediction (CSP) is: Given just a 2D molecular diagram, can we predict the most likely crystalline form or forms of a molecule and their properties? This is important because the crystal structure affects the material properties. For instance, for organic electronics, it affects charge transport and optical properties; and for porous materials, it affects porosity, stability, and selectivity.

One package to automate the CSP workflow is mol-CSPy³⁹, using Python. The tool takes the 2D molecular information and automates calculation of 3D conformations, including generating thousands of unique possible structures and using a molecular mechanics model to rank them. Chris concluded by explaining that this CSP workflow is very powerful, reliable, and scalable, but it creates large quantities of crystal structure data and properties, and this is accelerating. Therefore, one important goal is to establish a central database of curated CSP information as well as related tools and make both the data and the software more FAIR.

Simon Coles, University of Southampton, “Data management and FAIR standards: A crystallographer’s perspective”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AZUIYEHpzS44oZXF3mQAh3ulbGIFTvXr/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Simon Coles is a Professor of Structural Chemistry and the Director of the UK National Crystallography Service at the University of Southampton, as well as the Principal Investigator of PSDI (“one of the proud parents of PSDI, who was there at the inception of the project,” as he put it). Simon gave a talk on data management and FAIR standards from a crystallographer’s perspective.

Echoing some of the points in Ian’s talk at Cambridge, Simon stressed that crystallography has been an exemplar of how to collect and curate research data well, using community-accepted disciplinary standards.

³⁹ Mol-CSPy in GitHub: <https://gitlab.com/mol-cspy/mol-cspy>

Simon started with a quote from J.D. Bernal from 1948: “The collective use of data would lead to the discovery of new knowledge which transcends the results of individual experiments.” To establish the timeline of developments, he spoke about the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) for organic and metal-organic molecules, which started as a series of printed volumes in libraries (1965); and about other early databases in chemistry, including Inorganic Crystal Structure Database for inorganic compounds (1978) and Protein Data Bank for biological macromolecules (1971).

Simon used a data graph to illustrate the exponential growth in the volume of research data produced in the discipline, with instrumentation automation, the internet, and digital information partly responsible for this swift upward trend – and the use of data growing from derivation of reference values, through identifying preferences for interactions, to predicting crystal structures (see slides 4 and 5 from Simon’s talk below).

Next, again echoing Ian’s talk in Cambridge, Simon talked about the introduction of Crystallographic Information File (CIF) in 1990, designed for “archiving and information interchange standard for crystallographic and related structural science data” under the authority of an IUCr Committee, and the unifying, transformative impact that CIF had on the

field of crystallography. He also stressed that CIF – and later the broader Crystallographic Information Framework – were so influential because they were universally adopted: “full stakeholder buy-in across the whole data lifecycle,” from experimental data to structural knowledge.

Simon talked about the timeline of developments toward FAIR crystallography – and how new methods are stretching this framework and calling for new approaches. Dynamic crystallography is crystallography where you do something to the sample and study how the sample changes. We can learn a lot more that way.

Simon also argued that the quality of the data matters less than its usefulness to answer a specific research question. We don't always need highly accurate data. Instead, we need to think about the ways that the data will be used. The bottom line: data should be fit for purpose.

What are some drivers for better data management in crystallographic research?

- More challenging samples
- More challenging experiments
- New structure determination methods
- New structure refinement methods
- New structure analysis methods

Simon concluded by stating that the field of crystallography research is changing again. These changes include the rise of AI and ML, the opportunity to integrate crystallographic data with other data, possibly learning and then predicting structure-property relationships and conducting multi-modal studies without the need for expensive instrumentation. The key to adapting to these changes lies in AI-ready FAIR and open data, open software, open standards, automated validation, strong governance, a connected information chain, collections that can drive new science, a strong and cohesive community – and above all, keeping an open mind.

A lively discussion followed. One participant asked if, in this case, the software (CIF and the tools that read it) created the community. Simon responded that the software definitely created the community. The standard was integrated into the software, and the widespread adoption of the same software (and the same standard) brought the community together and unified it. Another participant commented that the dissemination of the software was done through summer schools, which means that young scientists were taught how to use it, a very effective method to convert the entire community. The group also discussed the differences between wet labs and analytical environments, and the disconnect between these two. There is more fragmentation in the field as well. How you generate a crystal structure determines which area of crystallography it belongs to. Finally, a lot depends on the instrument and software standards. Open standards would be ideal, but the vendors are often not keen on making their file formats open.

Matthew Partridge, University of Southampton, “Balancing Trust and Verification: Data auditing as the backbone of reliable chemistry data”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/17-XLY7jNdMOFLg7IeHvtLpiOQOIhaGK1/view?usp=sharing>

Dr Matthew Partridge is at the University of Southampton and works on PSDI Pathfinder 3, which aims to develop robust data collections in physical sciences as well as case studies on how to best build and use these data collections. Matthew spoke about data auditing as the backbone of reliable chemistry data and the challenge of balancing trust and verification.

To set the context, and drawing on his experience in building and curating data collections in physical chemistry, Matthew pointed out the key tasks involved:

- Developing robust methods to build, store, manage, and export diverse data
- Aggregating and standardizing data from various sources, including institutional repositories
- Providing datasets for identified applications from aggregated data collections
- And providing case studies on these methodologies

Matthew used the Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection⁴⁰ – and specifically a dataset of melting points – to illustrate the challenges of building a data collection that includes data from a range of existing sources. Data auditing has been a necessary step to make the collection reliable, traceable, usable, and consistent. The aim is also to offer information that is machine-readable.

⁴⁰ The Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection:

<https://resources.psd.ac.uk/data/44160b2f-5938-442e-9f0a-652eb55d1c2b>

The following main questions guide the data audit – each question presenting unique difficulties along the way:

- What is the source of the data?
- Is the data complete and understood? (e.g., Is it the entire, self-contained thing, or do we need additional data to make sense of it?)
- Can we use this data? (e.g., Is it legally permitted, as per usage license?)

Matthew concluded with a strong recommendation to always verify the source of the data, the data itself, and the usage conditions (including licensing and citations).

Richenda Houseago-Stokes, “Oceanographic Data Management”

Presentation slides:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1cMCJUH5VUCsdZgTLujqdlBnf_X50Zah/view?usp=sharing

Dr Richenda Houseago-Stokes is the Senior Data Manager at the British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC), which is the UK National Marine Data Centre as well as an accredited Data Archive Centre with the Marine Environmental Data & Information Network (MEDIN).

Richenda talked about oceanographic data management at the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS), which is a network of five data centres, with domain specific expertise, of which BODC is one centre. A graphic summary of the usage and other Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the five data centres is given below (slide 4 of Richenda’s presentation).

Richenda talked about the importance of research data lifecycle and data management planning in her discipline, and discussed the EDS Data Management Plan, which is tailored to environmental data. The DMP template is colour coded to encourage researchers to follow the FAIR data principles (red for not FAIR, green for FAIR), it allows for collaboration, versioning is built in (i.e., who changed what and when), and the final DMP can be exported as a pdf.

Richenda also gave an overview of the Marine Environmental Data & Information Network (MEDIN), which is the long-term, open partnership to manage UK marine data, with 16 sponsors and over 60 partners, and “the single place to find all UK marine data.” The motto of MEDIN is: “measure once, use many times.” MEDIN provides resources and services that support all four FAIR principles when it comes to research data: a discovery portal (Findable), accredited data centres (Accessible), the Marine Discovery Metadata Standard (Interoperable), and MEDIN Data Guidelines (Reusable). Training is also offered in a variety of formats to equip the marine researchers and support staff with skills to make their datasets and other research outputs FAIR.

Richenda concluded her talk with a list of considerations, in the form of guiding questions, when selecting and using a data repository.

Louise Saul, University of Southampton, “Data stewardship and the role of technicians/research technical professionals”

Presentation slides:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1sDt2h-tqyt6sswtoTgqOQzRE4QH65DfJ/view?usp=sharing>

The last presentation of the day came from Dr Louise Saul from the University of Southampton. Louise spoke about the crucial but often underestimated role of technicians/research technical professionals (RTPs) in data stewardship in physical sciences and emphasized the need for more recognition as well as more opportunities for technicians and RTPs to contribute their expertise.

Louise also discussed The Technician Commitment and its four goals: visibility, recognition, sustainability, and career development for technicians and RTPs. Advancing these goals is increasingly important because of the growing range of responsibilities that technicians and RTPs have in research projects: from facilities management, through training and support, to being members of research teams and holding often very specialized expertise in specific instrumentation and techniques. Similarly, the skills, knowledge, and responsibilities associated with data stewardship continue to expand – from awareness of organisational culture and industry standards, through knowledge of data collection, data storage, and how to maintain data quality, to strategic thinking and communication with users. Given the specialized expertise of technicians and RTPs and their role in data stewardship, their input into data management and data curation could strengthen research projects in multiple ways.

Louise offered several suggestions on how to both support technicians and RTPs – and more fully utilize their expertise and experience:

- Engage with technicians/RTPs as soon as possible in the project
- Ensure that you are aware of the remit and experience of technical staff
- Discuss costs for management and storage of data
- Think of the role of data steward (as played by technicians/RTPs)
- Are the technicians/RTPs sufficiently supported in their responsibilities?
- Work to design Continued Professional Development (CPD) on data practices for technicians/RTPs
- Uphold The Technician Commitment
- Promote visibility of technicians/RTPs by seeking their input

Highlights from Small-group Discussions

As in Cambridge, the next part of the Southampton event consisted of moderated small-group discussions. We used the same set of discussion questions as in Cambridge (shared in **Appendix B**). The purpose of having discussion questions was to guide the discussion and stay on topic, but we allowed enough flexibility to follow the participants' unique interests and experiences for a more natural conversation. Printed worksheets and a digital file for collaborative notes were provided. One or more PSDI, DCC, or University of Southampton staff members served as a moderator and note taker at each table.

Data curation vs. data management

Similar to the Cambridge event, the small-group discussions in Southampton revealed that participants held different definitions of data curation and data management among them.

One view defines data management as data-related tasks done during a research project, until the project goals are achieved; while data curation comes into play after the project is done and the data is shared with the wider scientific community. Another way to think about it: data management aims to get the data in the right state to answer the research question of the project (first) and prepare the data to share with the community (second). Data curation happens when the data is actually shared with the community. On this view, in terms of the actors involved, data management is done by the project team (e.g., data manager or data steward), while data curation is done by data repositories.

One participant offered this distinction: "Curation refers to someone else's data. You don't curate your own data. You curate data that came from somewhere else. Not your own project." Another participant stressed the different actions involved: "Data curation is looking after the data. Data management is doing something with the data."

A different view allows for some overlap. In the words of one participant: "data management is the plan that encompasses all stages in data lifecycle" while "data curation is the part that comes after data creation" but overlaps with data management after that.

However, in yet another view, data management is the broader concept and data curation fits inside it. In the words of one participant, "I think of curation as part of management. You prepare your data for analysis."

Different roles may also have different knowledge of and perspective on the topic. For instance, research technicians may know a lot about data collection and the instruments used, but not much about the rest of the project or what happens to the data after the project wraps up. To them, the term *data management* is more familiar than *data curation*. In fact, as one participant observed, "if we asked 1000 people if they are doing data management or data curation, most people would answer they are doing data management." The JISC Research Data Lifecycle (see the summary of Samantha Pearman-Kanza's talk) includes a "manage, store, and preserve" stage but does not mention curation.

Data collections are an interesting case. Would building a collection fall under data curation? One participant observed that curation can start before the collection is made or finished. An analogy would be sorting whites and darks straight away rather than sorting them when they go into the wash.

Challenges & pain points (and some possible solutions)

The Southampton event participants listed many challenges and pain points in both data curation and data management in physical sciences.

Access to data—whether for the original data analyses or later on for reuse—is a challenge. Data can be in multiple places. What is needed is an overarching service that allows researchers to access and work with the data in an easy, frictionless manner.

Attribution and citations are also challenging and becoming more so. Attribution is about giving credit to the authors of the material (e.g., data) that is reused, and it is a requirement of many open licenses. Citation is more about providing the source of the material. One participant pointed out that researchers using the Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) cite the database instead of the specific piece of research they accessed there. The participant suggested “a more granular curation” and using metadata to refer to a particular research output. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are another possible solution. The goal is to make citing data the norm, but that requires a culture change.

On the other hand, sometime data for one analysis is taken from 100 different datasets, which means that the researcher needs to attribute and/or cite all these sources. As one participant put it: “Moving from a manual analysis with 100 data points to 10,000 data points using a machine. How do you attribute each point of data creation?” Perhaps umbrella PIDs that collect multiple DOIs could be used to identify large datasets compiled from multiple sources, to make the reuse and attribution & citation easier.

On the topic of PIDs: PIDs for instruments and equipment used in data collection would be very useful and help standardize the metadata and other documentation. A related challenge has to do with datasets collected over time, with possible upgrades or other changes to the instruments. How to document these changes? And where to draw the line between an upgrade vs. a different type of instrument?

Selecting useful, appropriate metadata to make your data reusable is still a challenge and requires specialized skills. While the person responsible for this task may know the metadata for their own area of research or the research area they are supporting, it is difficult to predict how the data may be reused by someone in a different research area and for completely different purposes. How to facilitate this cross-domain findability of data is still an open question. Maybe there could be a community-based process of continuous expansion of metadata based on the reuse of a dataset. What new metadata is relevant to a specific instance of reuse? Instead of putting the task solely on the original creators of the data.

Metadata also needs a hierarchy to be useful for discovery and reuse. Again, this requires specialized skills. The structure of metadata is important, and a README file is required for humans to understand that structure.

Another question is: Where to put the data to enable discovery and reuse? Several participants voiced concerns about institutional repositories not being a good place due to the data not being visible enough and a very basic metadata capture. Institutional repositories came about because of a funder requirement that institutions show commitment to open science, and this was a minimum step toward it. But in practice, these repositories are often not well run and do not offer enough support to researchers. Perhaps PSDI could help institutional repositories “to up their game” in terms of data curation?

Time and cost of data curation and data management is a challenge as well. Both activities are often underestimated and undervalued. When planning a research project and applying for funding, it may be better and cheaper to write that time and cost into the project from the start rather than hire a post-doc researcher later.

Roles & responsibilities in data curation

Who is responsible for managing and taking care of the data? This is a complicated question, and the answers will differ between institutions based on their culture, funding, and staffing. But the sole responsibility for the data should not be down to the researcher. Institutional memory and shared responsibility are more reliable than individual memory and individual responsibility. A single team member may leave and take all their knowledge with them.

It is in the institution's interest to look after their intellectual property (IP), and most institutions recognize it and have mechanisms to do this. This could be one motivation to manage and curate research data and other research outputs well – because they are valuable IP. But a cultural shift is needed to accomplish this. The legal team at a university is not typically involved with research data. Should they be involved early on and consulted on the data management plans (DMPs)?

Another question: How to assign responsibility at an institutional level? One way is for research teams to include the costs of data curation in their funding proposals and plan for it from the start. Another way is to assign staff members with the right technical expertise to work with the domain experts (researchers) to support data curation. At the University of Southampton, some research software engineers are now assigned to support data curation.

While the responsibility for data curation is shared, there is still a role for a *data curator*. Ideally, that curator would be involved and advise from the very beginning, to help plan the creation or collection of the data. Similarly, there is a role for a *data manager*. Using their skills and knowledge, the data manager could “speak for the data” and make decisions about what happens to the data. Finally, trained *data stewards* could be involved in both data management and data curation and ensure longevity and continuity of both activities beyond individual research projects. There is a great need for professional data stewardship.

Funders and research councils also have a role to play in encouraging or demanding best practices in both data management and data curation. But these stakeholders need to be informed about what is needed and why. This information should come from the professional research support staff: data curators, data managers, data stewards. This requires that these staff members can sit at the same table as funders and research councils and be included in the conversation; this way, they can directly communicate the needs and challenges in the research areas they support and help design the solutions.

AI and automation in data curation

Participants agreed that there is a role for AI/ML in supporting data curation and data management – but it is imperative to remember that AI/ML is not a “magical fix.” They are only tools. Human experts still need to check and validate the outputs, paying careful attention to domain-specific nuances. Small, targeted AIs designed and trained to do a specific task could be very useful. One example: PSDI's Data Revival service which scans and translates handwritten research notes into a machine-readable content.

But the current AI tools have many limitations and, in the words of one participant, “AI is not good at something it hasn’t seen before.” In addition, ethical and legal concerns abound and necessitate caution, e.g., around human data.

In addition to the potential for AI/ML to assist with and improve data curation and data management tasks, there is also the opposite direction of influence: good data management and good data curation enabling better AI/ML projects. This bidirectional relationship is sometimes referred to as “AI for FAIR and FAIR for AI.” Participants pointed out that high-quality AI/ML projects require high-quality data management and curation, including better indexing and cataloguing of data. Otherwise, it’s the “garbage in, garbage out” principle.

How could PSDI support data curation?

Participants had a range of suggestions regarding how PSDI could support data curation in physical sciences in the UK.

One suggestion was for PSDI to put together a realistic timeline of activities and gather evidence to show progress with respect to promoting and supporting best practices in data curation. It is important for PSDI to work closely with other stakeholders to decide who is responsible for which task, what is in scope and what is not, and how the community is defined. Equally important will be assessment of impact.

One important goal will be to convince researchers, research support staff, and other stakeholders why they should buy into these efforts. This buy-in will depend on PSDI being able to demonstrate to institutions the real value and tangible benefits of data curation. Case studies that show the importance of data curation could be especially compelling here and could also be used to apply for funding to support data curation roles.

PSDI could also help advance best practices in data curation by developing and offering a coherent set of domain-specific tools and resources, e.g., DMPs tailored to physical sciences. PSDI could also gather existing domain knowledge and technical skills and serve as an authoritative source of information on research data in physical sciences. Case studies can serve as important exemplars. Training courses and materials also play a crucial role. PSDI does not have to develop their own training, but they can identify and promote high-quality training produced by others to the wider PSDI community.

Feedback Survey

To gather participants’ feedback and suggestions about the Southampton event, we again used a Google Form survey that included ranking questions (to obtain quantitative data) and open-ended questions (to obtain qualitative data). The survey was adapted from the Cambridge event survey. A copy of the Southampton survey and a summary of results are provided in **Appendix D**.

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

The primary aim of the PSDI Roadshow events in Cambridge and Southampton was to gather community input on data curation and data management in physical sciences in the UK. This

aim was successfully accomplished. Both events succeeded in bringing together a diverse group of stakeholders, in providing a forum for knowledge exchange and community discussion, and in gathering valuable insights into the current practices, challenges, and opportunities in data curation and data management in physical sciences, with life sciences and environmental sciences serving as useful benchmarks.

The knowledge and insights gained during the events will feed directly into the work on data curation guidelines for physical sciences, co-led by CCDC, DCC, and PSDI. A separate, more focused report will synthesize this work, including an overview of existing data curation guidelines and best practices, and relevant case studies.

A related and equally important aim of the Roadshow events was to collect community inputs on how PSDI could support and advance data curation and data management in physical sciences in the UK. This aim was achieved as well.

Based on participants' recommendations, PSDI could contribute to the development and adoption of best practices in data management and data curation in physical sciences by:

- Developing and offering a coherent set of domain-specific tools and resources, e.g., DMPs tailored to physical sciences.
- Gathering existing domain knowledge and technical skills and serving as an authoritative source of information on research data in physical sciences.
- Gathering case studies of such best practices to serve as exemplars.
- Developing their own training courses and materials on the relevant topics and to build the required knowledge and skills, or alternatively, identifying and promoting high-quality training produced by others.
- Working closely with community stakeholders to accurately represent their needs and interests, draw on their expertise, and stay current on new developments in the field.
- Serving as a community hub for physical sciences research in the UK by organizing events to facilitate knowledge exchange, networking, and community building.
- Establishing direct communication channels and collaborations with physical-science academic departments and professional bodies across the UK to raise awareness of PSDI's work and encourage engagement.
- Working closely with data repositories, academic publishers, and funders.
- Serving as a bridge between academia and industry in the UK.
- Setting realistic goals and timelines, assessing their progress and impact along the way, and sharing that evidence with stakeholders to build trust and authority.

In closing, we want to express our sincere gratitude to all the co-organizers, speakers, and participants of both PSDI Roadshow events for their contributions.

6 Appendices

Appendix A: Cambridge Event Web Page

The web page and main promotion emails included the following information about the Cambridge event. The event agenda was also given (see the main body of the report).

Event Description

The [Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\)](#), the [Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre \(CCDC\)](#), and the [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#) are jointly hosting an in-person, one-day event to explore data curation and data management in physical sciences.

Via presentations and discussions, the event will enable knowledge exchange around current practices, challenges, and future directions in the curation and management of research data in physical sciences, as well as foster networking and collaboration.

The event will highlight PSDI's work and, importantly, gather community input for identifying future priorities and activities that will support data management and curation in the physical sciences.

The event is part of the PSDI UK Roadshow on Data Curation and Data Management in Physical Sciences. [Click here to see our Southampton event.](#)

Event is free to attend, and lunch will be provided. But spaces are limited, so please make sure you [register here](#).

For any questions, please contact us at psdi@soton.ac.uk.

Who Should Attend?

This event is intended primarily for the academic research community in physical sciences, including:

- Data repository managers
- Data stewards
- Academic librarians and other research support professionals
- Research technicians
- Researchers with an active interest in generating, managing, and reusing research data
- Other data professionals involved or interested in curating and managing data

Our regional focus is on the Cambridge area and surrounding regions.

Why Attend?

- Exchange knowledge on data curation and data management in physical sciences in the era of automation and AI
- Contribute your experience and perspective to help shape best practices and community guidelines
- Connect with professional peers in your discipline and region
- Discover PSDI's work, influence its future priorities, and learn how you can get involved

What is PSDI?

The [Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\)](#) aims to provide a data infrastructure that connects existing experimental and computational facilities within the physical sciences and beyond. In the long term, PSDI aims to enable:

- A platform for data collection, sharing, aggregation, integration, and curation
- Support for analysis across experimental, simulation, and reference data

- Combining and enhancing existing data infrastructures
- Sustaining data resources beyond the lifespan of individual research projects

The event web page also included travel directions and the event agenda.

Appendix B: Discussion Questions (Cambridge & Southampton)

Provided below are the discussion questions used to guide the discussion and gather participants' inputs, experiences, and ideas at the Cambridge and Southampton events.

Introductions

Affiliation, current role (and past ones, if relevant), and your involvement in data curation and/or management.

Discussion 1: Data Curation and Management

- What is data curation?** How would you define it? What is involved?
- How does data curation differ from / relate to data management and data preservation?** How important is this distinction?
- Main challenges and pain points?** Consider research data curation and management in general – and specifically in physical sciences (or your area).

Discussion 2: Roles and Responsibilities

Stakeholders to consider: Researchers, Data Stewards, Research Support Staff, Institutional Repositories, General Data Repositories, Domain Repositories, Community curators, Publishers, Others?

- Who is responsible for data curation and data management?**
- What skills and strengths do different stakeholders offer?**
- Role of AI/Machine Learning?** How can AI/ML support data curation/management? What is needed from data curation/management to facilitate AI/ML projects?
- What limitations in knowledge, tools, guidance are hindering best practice?**

Discussion 3: What could PSDI do?

Feel free to initially assume unlimited resources/boundaries but ultimately please prioritize what might be most impactful or most feasible.

- How could PSDI support data curation and data management in physical sciences?**
- What tools, resources, and training could they provide?**

Appendix C: Cambridge Survey

The PSDI Cambridge Event Participant Survey was build, administered, and analysed in Google Forms. The introduction and survey questions with response options are given below.

The PSDI Cambridge Event Participant Survey

Thank you for participating in the **Exploring Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences: PSDI Roadshow @ Cambridge** event on 25th of June 2025. We are thrilled that you were able to attend!

Now we would love to hear about your experience. Your feedback and suggestions will help us improve similar events in the future. Thank you in advance for your time.

If possible, please fill out the survey by 11th of July 2025.

Q1. How would you rate the **overall event**?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Very good				

Q2. How would you rate the quality of **presentations**?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Very good				

Q3. Did any of the presentations stand out as particularly relevant, helpful, or inspiring? Which ones? Please comment.

Q4. Did you present a talk yourself at this event (either a lightning talk or a longer talk)?

- Yes
- Not this time

Q5. If you presented a talk, what was your experience? Any suggestions on how we could make the presenters' experience better in the future?

Q6. How would you rate the usefulness of **group discussions**?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Very good				

Q7. Please share any comments or suggestions about the group discussions. How could we improve them in the future?

Q8. How would you rate the usefulness of **networking** at this event?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Very good				

Q9. Please share any comments or suggestions about the networking. How could we improve it in the future?

Q10. Please share any additional comments about the event agenda or suggestions for similar events in the future.

Q11. How would you rate the overall **event organisation**, including the venue, catering, and communications?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very poor	<input type="radio"/>	Very good				

Q12. Please share any comments or suggestions about the conference organisation. How could we improve it for the future events?

Q13. What was the **most valuable aspect** of the event to you?

Q14. PSDI has a webinar series. Would you be interested in collaborating on a **webinar** on a topic of interest to you?

- Very interested
- Possibly
- Not at this time

Q15. If you are interested in giving a webinar, please provide your email and the topics you could speak on - and we will get in touch. (*Please be aware that this means your responses will no longer be anonymous.*)

Q16. Please share any additional comments or suggestions about any aspect of the PSDI Cambridge event or about PSDI more generally.

Summary of Results from the PSDI Cambridge Event Survey

The survey garnered 5 responses. All five respondents rated the event as good or very good overall (2 or 40% good; 3 or 60% very good). Similarly, the quality of presentations was rated as good (1 or 20% of respondents) or very good (4 or 80% of respondents). Four out of five (or 80%) respondents were presenters at the event. One suggestion was to make the lightning talks 10-minute long rather than only 5-minute long.

The question about the usefulness of discussions garnered four responses, and all four respondents rated the usefulness as good (1 or 25%) or very good (3 or 75%). One suggestion on how to improve the discussions was to allow longer time (after the small-group breakout discussions) for the whole group to come together to discuss. Alternatively, each small group could focus their discussion on only one issue and then present to the larger group.

When asked about the usefulness of networking at this event, 2 out of 5 (or 40%) of respondents rated it as very good, 2 (40%) as good, and 1 (20%) was neutral on the issue. One respondent commented that “similar events should be organized at local and national/international levels” and involve students, researchers, facility staff, and research councils.

The overall event organization was also rated as good (2 out of 5 or 40% of respondents) or very good (3 or 60% of respondents). One respondent commented: “I only found out about this meeting a few days beforehand. I think it would be of interest to many. I work in the life sciences, and it became apparent that we share the same challenges as the physical sciences; I think we can share our experience and knowledge.”

When asked about the most valuable aspect of the event to them, the respondents listed networking and group discussion, as well as learning about the databases and about the templates for data management plans. One respondent also commented on the role of facilities and technicians: “It also reinforced my idea that Facilities should be directly involved as a link between users and data repositories. I think there is knowledge and transferrable skills among librarians and facility technicians that could be very helpful for such operations.” Another respondent offered this summation: “Really good speakers at a small meeting – a great opportunity to really talk and learn from each other.”

Appendix D: Southampton Survey

The PSDI Southampton Event Participant Survey was build, administered, and analysed in Google Forms.

The PSDI Southampton Event Participant Survey

We reused the Event Participant Survey from the Cambridge event, with minimal changes (e.g., location name). Please see **Appendix C** above for the survey questions.

Summary of Results from the PSDI Southampton Event Survey

The survey garnered 4 responses. When rating the event overall, 2 respondents (50%) rated is as very good, one (25%) as good, and one (25%) was neutral. When asked to rate the quality of presentations, two respondents (50%) rated it as very good and two (50%) as good. In open-ended responses, one respondent commented: “Interesting to see the many aspects of data management across the physical sciences and the challenges faced.” Another said: “I found the one [presentation] on metadata very useful as it pointed out some really good resources and approaches.”

Out of the 4 respondents, two were presenters at the event. Both had a good experience presenting. One pointed out that lining up the talks ahead of time and presenting from the same computer worked well and reduced the setup time between talks.

The opinions about the usefulness of group discussions were more mixed. Two respondents (50%) rated that usefulness as very good and one respondent (25%) as good, but one rating (also 25%) said “poor.” One respondent commented: “Although we had questions set for the group discussions, we started on these, but ended up achieving more when we talked about learned experiences and issues.” Another respondent pointed out that the discussions

required more time and “the feedback from the facilitators was a bit disappointing as they seemed to not really know what they wanted from us” and suggested that the discussions came “maybe too early in the process?” In terms of logistics, “it [was] great having the notes recorded into the shared document, rather than spending too long on briefing back as that gave more time for discussions.”

When rating the usefulness of networking at the event, two respondents out of 4 (50%) rated it as very good, one (25%) as good, and one was neutral on the issue. One respondent commented: “I think for the scale of this event it was great. I don’t think it needed any engineering because there were a lot of great people and the skills of the PSDI team.”

In terms of the event agenda, one respondent shared this suggestion: “I wouldn’t have had the presentations from individual researchers [...] and would have stuck to the PSDI related work and information about the network. Another commented: “Rather selfishly, but it might be good to have a deep dive into people’s experiences of setting up data management systems.”

When asked about the overall event organization, the ratings were again split. One respondent (25%) rated it as very good and two (50%) as good, but one rating (25%) said “poor.” One respondent commented: “It all came together at the end from the external participants point of view I believe, but from a behind-the-scenes view was very last minute in its preparation.” Two respondents also commented on the event location and the difficulty of finding the event space: “Signage was poor. Entry to the building was mystifying.” And: “The only slight hitch was getting entry to the building.”

When asked about the most valuable aspect of the event to them, the respondents listed networking, both presentations and discussions, and learning about the PSDI (including what to do and what not to do for other data infrastructure projects).

In summing up the event, one respondent shared this insight: “‘don’t reinvent the wheel’ was the phrase of the day, but in lots of ways you could be drawing more on existing networks around the UK and I was astonished that there were none there on the day to present on their experiences.” Another respondent ended with thanks and encouragement: “Thanks so much for these great events, looking forward to more!”